

DMP Assistant Institutional Customization Guide

Version 1.0

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Developed by members of
the Portage DMP Customization Working Group

portage@carl-abrc.ca

www.carl-abrc.ca

portage
SERVICES PARTAGÉS POUR LES DONNÉES DE RECHERCHE
SHARED STEWARDSHIP OF RESEARCH DATA

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Introduction

The purpose of this document is to instruct local administrators of the modifications that can be made to DMP Assistant, in order to customize its content and appearance to meet their local institutional needs. The following guide introduces the organizational administrative interface, and demonstrates how it can be used to modify DMP Assistant templates (questions and guidance), as well as the “look and feel” of the GUI.

1. Preparing for customization

To get started with customizing DMP Assistant for your local institution, you will need the following:

- An institutional space within DMP Assistant. This can be requested from the Portage Network by contacting portage@carl-abrc.ca. With an institutional space, a local administrator will have administrative rights to edit basic organizational information and to implement some local customization options. It is recommended that a generic user account be used for administration, as it will reduce the possibility of accidentally transferring administrative privileges between user accounts;
- An individual designated as your institution’s DMP Assistant local administrator;
- Your institution’s logo image with a maximum height of 80 px;
- A CSS file based on the current [template](#) and modified according to the [instructions provided in Section 2](#);
- The [hexadecimal colour codes](#) for branding colours commonly used by your institution (to be used in the CSS file); and,

- (*Optional*) A top banner image with a height between 90 px to 160 px ([example](#))

For management and accessibility reasons, we ask that you only customize the elements that are described in this guide, using the provided methods. In the case that additional customization is desired, please contact portage@carl-abrc.ca.

2. Accessing and using the organizational administrative interface

As an organization's local administrator, you can log in and use the organization admin interface to manage your institutional space.

Once you have entered the organizational administrative interface, you will be able to:

1. Edit organization details;
2. View basic information for users associated with your organization (email address, last time of log-in, and the number of plans they have created);
3. Create, edit, manage and delete organization specific templates; and,
4. Create, edit, manage and delete organization specific guidance.

2.1 Accessing the organizational administration interface

Once logged into DMP Assistant with your administrator account, click on **Signed in as ...** and then select **Admin area** to access the organizational administration interface.

Figure 1: Click on **Admin area** to access the organizational administration interface

Figure 2: The organizational administrative interface.

2.2 Editing organization details

As the local administrator, you may view and edit the information for your organization. Please note, for the time being, not all features are enabled. To edit organizational details:

Click on **Organization details** to view your organization's basic profile information

Figure 3: Click on **Organization details** to view your organization's basic details

Click on the **Edit** button to edit the organization details.

Figure 4: Click on the **Edit** button to edit the organization details.

In the editable *organization details* page, local administrators can modify their organization's name, abbreviation, website URL, descriptive information, as well as upload an institutional logo, top banner image, and customized CSS file (see following sections).

Figure 5: The editable organizational details page.

Organisation details

Name: Portage

Abbreviation: Portage ?

Description: supporting Canadian innovation through shared expertise and stewardship of research data

Top banner text: [Rich text editor toolbar and empty text area]

Website: [Empty text box]

Organization type: Institution

Display In Registration:

Save Cancel

Figure 6: Editing organizational details

3. Customizing institutional logos, banners and color schemes

To create a local “look and feel” for DMP Assistant users logged-in with their particular institution, local administrators can modify one (or all) of the following elements: institutional logo; top banner image/color; and, institutional-specific color schemes (see Figure 7). The following guidance outlines these customization processes:

Figure 7: An example of a fully customized DMP Assistant interface

3.1 Preparing logo and banner images

For optimal presentation, your selected institutional/organizational logo image should have a maximum height of 80 px.

The use of a top banner background image ([example](#)) is optional. If you choose to use one, the image should have a height between 90 and 160 px for optimal presentation. Alternatively, you can forego the use of a banner image and instead customize the page CSS to select a solid background color for the banner area (see Section 2).

3.2 Uploading images to DMP Assistant

To upload the images, follow the steps below:

1. Login as administrator and follow the steps outlined in Section 1 to access the editable organization details page.
2. Prepare logo and banner images ([instructions](#)); customize your CSS file ([instructions](#)).
3. Use the interface to upload your customized logo, banner and CSS files into the administrative interface.

The screenshot shows a web form titled "Organisation details". It contains the following elements:

- Name:** University of British Columbia
- Abbreviation:** UBC
- Website:** http://researchdata.library.ubc.ca
- Description:** A large empty text area.
- Upload a new logo file:** A "Browse..." button and the text "No file selected."
- Upload a new top banner image:** A "Browse..." button and the text "No file selected."
- Upload a new customized stylesheet:** A "Browse..." button and the text "No file selected."
- Buttons:** "Save" and "Cancel" buttons located at the bottom right of the form.

Figure 8: Use the organizational details interface to upload customized logo, banner and CSS files.

3.3 Special notes on interface customization

For technical and administrative purposes, administrators should not modify the CSS code beyond that which is demonstrated in the following section (*GUI CSS customization*).

Other small changes may be possible on a case-by-case basis. If you require specific changes, please contact portage@carl-abrc.ca.

If a new image or CSS file is uploaded, the existing files will be overwritten. If you decide to switch back to original Portage logo/stylesheet and remove all customizations, please follow the directions on the interface. Check the checkboxes and click on **Save** to remove uploaded images, and click on the deletion link to remove uploaded CSS file.

4. GUI CSS customization

4.1 Overview

Using [McMaster University's customized CSS file](#) as a template, institutions can customize the colour scheme of DMP Assistant page using the CSS hexadecimal scheme. The thoroughly commented CSS template (providing additional annotations for each of the allowed colour changes) can be accessed and downloaded [here](#).

Before you begin editing the CSS file, you will need the hexadecimal colour codes commonly used by your institution. These begin with a # symbol and are followed by

six characters (numbers and/or letters). For example, white is #FFFFFF (or #FFF for short) and light grey is #333333.

Once you have your institution's colours, you can open the CSS template in a text editor (such as Notepad++) and start replacing the existing colours with your institution's colours.

To ensure you're using the correct hexadecimal colour scheme, you can use something like www.color-hex.com to verify.

Before you upload your revised CSS to DMP Assistant, ensure you have saved your file with the .css extension.

4.2 Example: Institutional CSS customization

The following example illustrates and documents the customization process, as applied by a single institution (McMaster University in this case). Screenshots were taken to show modifications made to the CSS code (with line numbers included, for easy reference), as well as the resulting changes to the interface. Each modification is presented in a separate section; screenshots of editable sections of the CSS file are shown first, followed by the resulting changes to the GUI. Please note that each modification has been applied independently, in order to better demonstrate the resulting effects.

4.2.1 Institutional hexadecimal colour codes

For the purposes of this example, McMaster's hexadecimal colour codes were found by consulting its [branding guide](#). The codes are as follows:

- #79133E-maroon
- #fff-white
- #990033-red

4.2.2 Section heading colour

Replace the hex colour code (#79133E) in the CSS snippet shown below with a desired colour.

```
4
5 h1, h2, h3, h4 {                               /*Header colour*/
6
7     color: #79133E;
8
9 }
```

Figure 9: Section heading changes in the CSS file

Figure 10: Resulting section heading colour changes in the GUI

4.2.3 Footer colour

Modify the hex colour codes for the footer banner (6 character hex code) and the footer text colour (3 character hex code).

```

22  footer{
23      background-color: #79133E;      /*footer banner colour*/
24  }
25  footer .right_side_footer p{      /*footer text colour*/
26      color: #fff;
27  }
28  .right_side_footer{                /*footer text colour*/
29      color: #fff;
30  }

```

Figure 11: Footer colour changes in the CSS file

Figure 12: Resulting footer colour changes in the GUI

4.2.4 Top banner text colour

Modify the hex colour code for the three lines shown below:

```

31 .header_center a{                               /*Shared Stewardship of Research Data text colour*/
32     color: #79133E;
33 }

37 h3.subhead{
38     color: #79133E;                               /*Language Setting colour*/
39 }
40 }

46 .signIn ul li a, .signIn ul li a.active, .signIn ul li a:visited {
47     color: #79133E;                               /*Sign in text colour*/
48 }

```

Figure 13: CSS file changes for the top banner colour (3 steps)

Figure 14: Resulting footer colour changes in the GUI

4.2.5 Colour of buttons and tables

```

19  .dmp_toolbar {                               /*filter plans box colour*/
20      background-color: #79133E;
21  }

42  body.dmponline .btn-primary, body.dmponline .btn-primary:active,
43      background: #79133E;                       /*buttons colour*/
44  }

50  body.dmponline .btn-primary:hover {
51      background: #990033;                       /*button colour when mouse hovers over it*/
52  }

54  table.dmp_table thead{                       /*table header colours*/
55      background-color: #79133E;
56  }

```

Figure 15: CSS file changes for the button and table colours (4 steps)

The screenshot shows the Portage web application interface. At the top left is the 'portage' logo with the tagline 'Shared stewardship of research data'. To the right, there is a language selector for 'Version française' and a user login status 'Signed in as RDM @McMaster'. Below these are navigation buttons: 'My plans', 'Create plan', 'About', and 'Help'.

The main content area is titled 'My plans'. Below the title is a brief description: 'The table below lists the plans that you have created, and any that have been shared with you by others. These can be edited, shared, exported or deleted at anytime.' Below this is a table with a search filter and a 'Filter' button. The table has the following data:

Name	Owner	Shared?	Last edited	Select an action
My plan (Portage Template)	Me	Yes (with 1 people)	23-10-2015	Edit Share Export Delete
My plan (Portage Template)	Me	No	05-01-2016	Edit Share Export Delete

Below the table is a 'Create plan' button. At the bottom of the page, there are logos for 'DMP ONLINE', 'CANADIAN ASSOCIATION OF RESEARCH LIBRARIES', 'UNIVERSITY OF ALBERTA LIBRARIES', and 'les bibliothèques/UdeM'. There is also a footer for 'Supported by UNIVERSITY OF ALBERTA LIBRARIES' and links for 'Web Site Privacy Policy | Terms'.

Figure 16: Resulting table and button colour changes in the GUI

4.2.6 Tab colour

Modify the hex colour code in the three lines shown below:

```

67
68 #project-tabs li.active a, #project-tabs li.active a:active, #project-tabs li a:hover{
69     background-color: #79133E;
70     border: 1px solid #79133E;    /*tab colours*/
71 }
72
73 .dmp_details_body{                /*tab border colour*/
74     border: 2px solid #79133E;
75 }

```

Figure 17: CSS file changes for tab colour

portage
Shared stewardship of research data

Version française

Signed in as RDM @McMaster

My plans Create plan About Help

My plan (Portage Template)

Plan details Portage Data Management Questions Share Export

This page gives you an overview of your plan. It tells what your plan is based on and gives an overview of the questions that you will be asked. [Edit plan details](#)

Plan name	My plan (Portage Template)
ID	-
Grant number	-
Principal Investigator/Researcher	RDM @McMaster
Plan data contact	-
Description	-

This plan is based on:

Institution	McMaster University
-------------	---------------------

[Answer questions](#) [Export](#)

Sections	Questions
Data Collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What types of data will you collect, create, link to, acquire and/or record? - What file formats will your data be collected in? Will these formats allow for data re-use, sharing and long-term access to the data? - What conventions and procedures will you use to structure, name and version-control your files to help you and others better understand how your data are organized?
	- What documentation will be needed for the data to be read and interpreted correctly in the future?

Figure 18: Resulting tab colour changes in the GUI

4.2.7 Question section colour

Modify the hex colour codes for the four lines shown below:

```

85
86  .accordion-group{ /*Question box colours*/
87     background-color: #79133E;
88     border-color:#79133E;
89  }
90
91  .accordion-heading{ /*Question box colours*/
92     background-color: #79133E;
93  }
94
95  .section-status{ /*Question box colours*/
96     background-color: #79133E;
97  }

```

Figure 19: CSS file changes for section colour

Figure 20: Resulting section colour changes in the GUI

4.2.8 Guidance and suggestion box colours

Modify the hex colour codes for the three lines shown below:

```

98
99  div.suggested-answer-border {      /*Suggested answer box border colour*/
100     border: 1px solid #79133E;
101
102  }
103  .question-guidance .guidance-accordion-body {
104     border: 1px solid #79133E;      /*Guidance box colour*/
105  }
106  .question-guidance .accordion-heading a, .question-guidance .accordion-heading a:hover{
107     color: #79133E !important; /*Guidance heading colour*/
108  }

```

Figure 21: CSS file changes for guidance and suggestion box colours

Figure 22: Resulting guidance and suggestion box colour changes in the GUI

4.2.9 Top banner background colour

To use a customized background color, add the following line to your CSS (replacing #c7e2fa with a hex colour code of your preference).

```
.dmponline {
    background-color: #c7e2fa;
}
```

5. Template customization and management

The Portage template can be regarded as a generic DMP template that can be used “out of the box” by any researcher. Not all institutions will need nor want to develop an institutional template, but the functionality is available for those who feel it is important for their organization. For those institutions wishing to provide customized templates (questions and guidance) to meet specific needs, the following steps demonstrate how a custom template can be created using the administrative interface.

5.1 Template management

The steps for template management follow the logical sequence of Template->Phase->Version->Section->Questions. Please note that at any point, you can preview the template by clicking on **Preview** under **Actions**.

5.1.1 Template

To create a new template, click on *Templates* on the top navigation, and then click on **Create a template**:

The screenshot shows the 'Templates' page. At the top, there is a 'Create a template' button. Below it, there is a table with the following data:

Title	Description	Published	Last updated	Actions
Portage Template	This is the generic DMP template for Portage.	true	19-10-2015	Edit

Figure 23: The Templates page allows you to view, edit or create new templates.

Provide title and description information for the new template, and then click on **Save**:

The screenshot shows the 'New template' form. The 'Title' field contains 'Test Template'. The 'Description' field contains 'This is a test template'. There is a 'Save' button and a 'Cancel' button at the bottom right.

Figure 24: Inserting title and description for a new template

5.1.2 Phase and version

Phases are used to indicate different stages of a research project (e.g. pre- / during / post-project). The generic Portage Template is not a phased template. To create a single phased template like the generic Portage Template, you only need to add a new phase once. Click on the *Add new phase+* tab to add a new phase of the

template. The phase title is what users will see in the tabs when completing a plan. If you only need one phase, you may wish to give it a generic title such as *<Your Institution>_ Data Management Questions*.

The screenshot shows a web interface titled "Test Template" with a "View all templates" button in the top right. Below the title is a navigation bar with "Template details" and "Add new phase +". The main content area is titled "Phase details" and contains the following information:

- Title:** Test DMP Questions
- Order of display:** 1
- Description:** A rich text editor with a toolbar containing bold (B), italic (I), text color (A), background color (A), bulleted list, numbered list, and link icons. A blue question mark icon is next to the editor.

At the bottom right of the form are "Save" and "Cancel" buttons.

Figure 25: Adding a phase to a template.

When a new phase is created, the creation of a new version of the template is triggered. For example, when the new phase is created for a new template, the first version of the template will be automatically created

To make major changes to a template that has already been published (such as adding a new section or series of questions), you should create a new version. To make small changes such as correcting typos, choose to edit the current version.

Click on **Save** to move on to creating sections and questions.

The screenshot shows a web interface for editing a 'Test Template'. At the top, there's a header 'Test Template' and a button 'View all templates'. Below the header, there are tabs: 'Template details', 'Test DMP Questions' (which is active), and 'Add new phase +'. The main content area is divided into three sections:

- Phase details:** Includes a description: 'Here you set the title that users will see. If you intend to have multiple phases for you DMP, this should be clear in the title and description.' and an 'Edit phase details' button. A table shows:

Title	Test DMP Questions
Order of display	1
Description	
- Versions:** Includes a description: 'A first version is created automatically. If you want to make major changes to published versions later (e.g. add section or questions) please create a new version. If you only want to fix typos or make small changes that do not alter meanings, edit the current version.' and a table:

Title	Published	Created at	Last updated	Actions
Test DMP Questions v.1	false	08-01-2016	08-01-2016	View Edit Preview
- Version details:** Includes a form for editing the current version. The 'Title' field contains 'Test DMP Questions v.1'. The 'Description' field has a rich text editor with a toolbar (bold, italic, text color, background color, list, link) and a text area. The 'Published' checkbox is unchecked. There are 'Save' and 'Cancel' buttons.

At the bottom of the page, there is a blue bar with a text input field 'New section title' and a '+' button.

Figure 26: The template details page.

5.1.3 Sections and questions

To add a new section, enter the section title at the bottom of the *Version editing* page, and click on **Add section**. Use the **+** to expand the section editing window for adding description information and to define the order in which the sections will be displayed.

Figure 27: Adding a new section.

Add questions to each section by selecting **Add question**.

Test Section 1

Order of display: 1

Description

Question number: 1

Question text

Answer format: Text area

Default answer

Suggested answer/Example: Example of answer

Save Delete Cancel

Guidance

Figure 28: Adding a new question.

When adding questions, you can:

- Use the *Question number* dropdown menu to define the display order of questions within a section: e.g. Question number 1 will be displayed first in the section. By changing the question number, the order in which the questions appear on the template will change accordingly.
- Choose the *Answer format*:
 - *text area* for long paragraphs of text;
 - *text field* for a short text answer;

- *checkbox* for presenting options for multiple value selection;
 - *radio button* for presenting options for single value selection;
 - *dropdown list* for controlled vocabulary selection;
 - *multiple select box* for allowing users to select multiple options from a scrollable list using the CTRL key.
- Define *default answer* for each question. The answer will be displayed in the answer box for users.
 - Define a *suggested answer* for each question. The example provided will be presented above the answer box and can be easily copied/pasted by the user.
 - Create question specific *guidance*. The guidance text entered here will always be displayed alongside the question, no matter what other guidance groups are selected (guidance groups are described in section 3.2.1).

5.1.4 Publishing

Once the sections and questions have been created, select the *Published* checkbox in the *Version editing* section to indicate the active version being used within your template. This step is necessary and indicates that the version is active and ready to be published as part of a template which itself must be published before it is made public.

The screenshot shows the 'Versions' management interface. At the top, there is a table with the following data:

Title	Published	Created at	Last updated	Actions
New template v.1	false	28-06-2016	28-06-2016	View Edit Preview

Below the table is the 'Version details' form. It includes a 'Title' field with the value 'New template v.1', a rich text editor for 'Description', and a 'Published' checkbox which is checked. A red box highlights the 'Published' checkbox. At the bottom right of the form are 'Save' and 'Cancel' buttons.

Figure 29: “Publish a version”, the checkbox is selected, then **save** to publish the template.

Once a version has been marked as *published*, return to the *Template details* tab. Select **Edit template details**.

Figure 30: “Template details” tab to access the template details editing page. Remember to first select a version of the template before proceeding to publish.

Figure 31: “Template details editing” page with the checkbox selected in order to publish the template.

Once the template is published, your users will see your new template as an available selection when they create a new DMP. The institutional template will be the default template and will be listed first in the dropdown selection menu.

Create a new plan

Please select from the following drop-downs so we can determine what questions and guidance should be displayed in your plan.

If you aren't responding to specific requirements from a funder or an institution, you can choose the **Portage Data Stewardship Template**. The Portage Data Stewardship Template is based on internationally accepted standards and best practices. It has been prepared and is maintained by a group of research data management experts from research libraries across Canada.

To see institutional questions and/or guidance, select your organization.

You may leave blank or select a different organization to your own. If you leave blank, default Portage DMP template will be used. Not applicable/not listed.

Choose a template

There are a number of possible templates you could use. Please choose one.

Figure 32: "Create a new plan" page showing two published templates as options.

Confirm plan details

You are using the generic Portage Data Stewardship template. If you have suggestions on how to improve the existing template, or if you would like to add additional templates based on funding agency requirements or disciplinary needs, please contact us at portage@carl-abrc.ca.

Institution: University of Alberta

Template: University of Alberta Template

Other guidance:

Figure 33: Confirmation dialogue box showing selection of customized institutional template.

5.2 Adding additional institutional guidance text

In some cases, it may be desirable or necessary to enhance a template's existing guidance text (e.g., the Portage template guidance) with additional, institutional-specific instructions.

In order to create institution-specific guidance text, local administrators must first create one or more *Guidance Groups*, to which guidance texts can be associated. Once this is done, the local administrator can generate an institutional guidance frame, which appears alongside the default template guidance in the GUI, by creating a guidance group guidance text.

1. You will need to first create a *Guidance Group* for your institution

Guidance group list

First create a guidance group. This could be institution wide or a subset e.g. a particular College / School, Institute or department. When you create guidance you'll be asked to assign it to a guidance group.

Guidance list

You can write pieces of guidance to be displayed by theme (e.g. generic guidance on storage and backup that should present across the board) or you can write guidance for specific questions. Writing generic guidance by theme saves you time and effort as your advice will be automatically displayed across all templates rather than having to write guidance to accompany each.

You will usually want your guidance to display on all templates, however there may be cases where you only want it to show for specific funders e.g. if you have specific instructions for applicants to BBSRC for example. This can be set too if needed.

Figure 34: *Guidance group list*, allowing the creation of new guidance groups and guidance text.

- You can identify which templates should be associated with a particular guidance group. You could create Portage and institution specific guidance as needed or generic guidance text that is applicable to all templates for users from your institution.
- If the guidance is only meant for a subset of your users, you can save the guidance as an optional subset. Users will be able to select whether or not to display this subset in the *create plan* wizard.

Guidance group

Name Label

Template
All templates
Portage Template
Test Template
University of Alberta Template

Optional subset e.g. School/ Department

Figure 35: *Assigning a guidance group to a template.*

- Once the guidance group is created, create individual guidance text by selecting **Add guidance**. You can draft guidance language to accompany specific questions.

Figure 36: Creating new guidance text.

- For guidance by question, you will need to indicate:
 - the template in which the question is found;
 - the phase of the template (e.g. phase for early vs. late part of the data management process);
 - the version of the template;
 - the section from the template in which the question is found; and,
 - the question to which the guidance will apply.

5.2.1 Previewing institution specific guidance

Figure 37: Click **Preview** to preview institutional specific guidance.

What types of data will you collect, create, acquire and/or record?

Save Not answered yet

UAlberta Guidance

Examples: Images, audio, video, text, tabular data, modeling data, spatial data, instrumentation data

Figure 38: A preview of institutional guidance.

5.2.2 Using institution specific guidance

1. On the *create plan* page, select your institution from the drop down menu.

Create a new plan

Please select from the following drop-downs so we can determine what questions and guidance should be displayed in your plan.

If you aren't responding to specific requirements from a funder or an institution, you can choose the **Portage Data Stewardship Template**. The Portage Data Stewardship Template is based on internationally accepted standards and best practices. It has been prepared and is maintained by a group of research data management experts from research libraries across Canada.

To see institutional questions and/or guidance, select your organization.

You may leave blank or select a different organization to your own. If you leave blank, default Portage DMP template will be used.

Create plan

Portage

Please select an organization:

- Portage
- University of Ottawa
- Concordia University
- McMaster University
- Scholars Portal
- University of Alberta
- University of British Columbia

Figure 39: Selecting an institution when creating a new plan.

2. Next, select the template to which the guidance applies.

Create a new plan

Please select from the following drop-downs so we can determine what questions and guidance should be displayed in your plan.

If you aren't responding to specific requirements from a funder or an institution, you can choose the **Portage Data Stewardship Template**. The Portage Data Stewardship Template is based on internationally accepted standards and best practices. It has been prepared and is maintained by a group of research data management experts from research libraries across Canada.

To see institutional questions and/or guidance, select your organization. [Not applicable/not listed.](#)
You may leave blank or select a different organization to your own. If you leave blank, default Portage DMP template will be used

Choose a template
There are a number of possible templates you could use. Please choose one.

Tick to select any other sources of guidance you wish to see.

McMaster

Figure 40: Selecting a template when creating a new plan.

3. Last, select the institution-specific guidance you wish to display (if it has been listed as an optional subset).

Create a new plan

Please select from the following drop-downs so we can determine what questions and guidance should be displayed in your plan.

If you aren't responding to specific requirements from a funder or an institution, you can choose the **Portage Data Stewardship Template**. The Portage Data Stewardship Template is based on internationally accepted standards and best practices. It has been prepared and is maintained by a group of research data management experts from research libraries across Canada.

To see institutional questions and/or guidance, select your organization. [Not applicable/not listed.](#)
You may leave blank or select a different organization to your own. If you leave blank, default Portage DMP template will be used

Choose a template
There are a number of possible templates you could use. Please choose one.

Tick to select any other sources of guidance you wish to see.

McMaster

Figure 41: Enabling additional guidance sources when creating a new plan.

It looks like this in the user interface:

Figure 42: Example of institutional-specific guidance during normal use.

4. Reporting issues/bugs and suggesting new features

All issues, bugs and new feature requests can be submitted via the *issues* page on DMP Assistant's GitHub page: https://github.com/ualbertalib/DMPOnline_v4/issues. In order to submit issues to the Github page, you must first have a Github user account (can be created at no cost).